

Theme of Religion Related to Christianity in 'Saint Joan'

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Abstract: *This paper aims to explore Bernard Shaw's religious ideas related to Christianity in the play 'Saint Joan'. In 'saint Joan' Shaw has presented a conflict between the Roman Catholic and Protestant through the church authority and Joan. As an individual Joan stands against the established authority like catholic church with brilliance and intellect. Through her journey from the beginning to the end, Shaw, directly and indirectly, presents the theme of religion. Through out the play "through his huge cast of varied human types, probes the whole range of belief and disbelief in Joan's voices". (P.16). Her tragic death lit a fire to the fuel of fighting of an individual against established authority like Church and their rules. Now we can proceed to discuss the theme of religion related to Christianity in 'Saint Joan'.*

Keywords: *Christianity, Religion, Individual Judgement, Conflict, Woman's voice.*

Introduction:

Shaw's play set in France in the 1400s, during the Hundred Years' war. The main story charts the rapid rise and fall of this young charismatic woman, Joan, who claims she has been instructed by God to liberate the captive city of Orleans. This intensity of Joan is reflected through her voice in the play 'Saint Joan':

God made them just like us; but he gave them their own country and their own language; and it is not his will that they should come into our country and try to speak our language. (P.70)

The way Joan approaches is the way of a protestant to establish Protestantism. So, Joan has to face a conflict between Catholic Church or established authority and individual judgment as presented in the play 'Saint Joan'. According to Duffin "Saint Joan is not only a great play, but a religious play one whose theme is compelling force of religious ideas". Truly, there are huge elements of religious order. In case of Joan, she is not ready to obey their rules but wants to act as a behalf of God. Joan says "How can you say that I am disobedient when I always obey my voices, because they come from God" (Shaw 122-23)

Shaw was a devoutly religious man. He considered religion as the life-blood of human civilization. A man without religion is considered by him as a coward. Thus, According to Carpenter, Shaw's plays reflect his interest in contemporary political, economic, sociological and religious issues. This interest becomes the dominant factor in the plays which continue Shaw's playwriting career. (P.7)

According to his biographers, Shaw was deeply interested in religion, and many of his plays are centrally concerned with religious themes. As a philosophical writer, he expressed his own ideas about politics, economics, religion and society. Same case occurs to Saint Joan. Joan is the mouthpiece of Shaw himself. Shaw was a Christian in his own way without being wedded to any particular order of the church. As a critic of the institutionalized form of religion, he attacked many of the established tenets and ecclesiastical practices. For him God is the source of all the creative forces. God is for him 'life-force'.

Shaw convinced of religion in terms of social values rather than in terms of spiritual redemption. To Shaw, religion involves political and social constitutions and the ends of civilization. As a dramatist, he combined both his socialistic and artistic interests in his plays. In this respect, the dramatic method in his plays is based on the conflict of ideas and beliefs from a socialist standpoint. As A. Charles

Carpenter remarked,

Shaw's protagonists in his dramatic works are mostly intellectuals whose roles are to propagate his socialist and religious ideas, while changing society as his agents of the life force. (P.7).

In the preface to the play 'Saint Joan' Shaw has clearly shown the quintessence of the Joanesque spirit, which echoes his own. The opposition between her and the church is virtually a combat between the creative religious convictions and the traditional prejudice bound life. Joan was against the institutionalized, authoritarian and hierarchical form of Christianity. Shaw also believed that the priestly-classes' claim of being direct representative of God is nothing but a gross distortion of fact. If religion leads to inner growth and spiritual uplift, the so called intermediary position of the priest-class is obviously unimportant. "And there is hardly any necessity of spiritual spoon-feeding by the priestly class". (1987.p.8)

Joan and the Church stand as irresistible forces and immovable objects. They are the representatives of God on Earth. But in the Middle Ages people believed in it as they believed in the moon or the sun. The significance of Church again and again brought out by the Bishop. But this is not the only point Joan comes into conflict with society. Joan considers herself as the messenger of God. Under no circumstances she is ready to stomach the idea that someone is defying her orders because she is ministering agent of God.

Shaw in the play shows us the sense of desperate necessity under which the inquisition weighed the case of Joan. It is felt that the church was threatened by the rise of Protestantism represented by Joan. Thus, according to Bloom Joan's apparent resemblance to the Aristotelian hero, "her extreme self-confidence, her brashness, her appearance of rash impetuosity" (1987.P.16) is clearly revealed. Louis L. Martz, in his essay "The Saint as Tragic Hero", argues that "Joan embodies a unique form of tragic heroism that challenges traditional definitions." For her only real error in the play is the one point where her superb self-confidence breaks down in the panic of recantation. According to Desmond Macarthy "The essence of the theme is the struggle of religion".

Conclusion:

To conclude we may say that in the middle ages, religious faith was a living, breathing reality. It was the very breath of life. At the same time Joan with her reliance on individual judgment and inspiration comes into headlong clash with this all powerful organization. She represents a force greater than herself; everything about her shows that she is guided by a power tastes than her individual self. Thus Shaw presents a clash between the Protestant Maiden and the all powerful Roman Catholic Church, and the result is a poignant and moving tragedy. But in 1920 Joan is declared to be a Saint by the Church. Indeed, she invokes the name of God with such regularity that she is rebuked by the Archbishop. In the play 'Saint Joan' Shaw presents to the reader his concept of God. Thus, Shaw's attitude towards religion and Christianity is clearly seen in the play 'Saint Joan'. Through Joan's voice Shaw highlights the eternal struggle between individual conscience and institutional authority, a tension that persists in modern social and political structures. Besides, Joan symbolizes the spirit of independent judgement and the courage to stand by one's personal truth against a powerful organization. Her ultimate canonization in 1920 serves as an alarm that the light of truth may be suppressed initially, but one day the truth comes out through the chest of darkness, making her a timeless symbol.

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